

METHODS OF FORMING A CRITICAL OPINION

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ABSTRACT: Given article is dedicated to questions of the shaping the critical thinking pupils in process of the study of the literary product. In her are determined pedagogical conditions of the shaping beside pupils independent estimation of the artistic product, in count, calculate, list which is named interaction of the teacher and pupils in the course of analysis of the artistic text, enrichment pupils literary knowledge, development to independent activity pupils and the main - a critical approach to estimation of the product and his (its) heroes.

Keywords: Artistic product, literary hero, analysis, critical thinking, estimation, methods of the teaching, creative activity, literature skills, aesthetic estimation.

INTRODUCTION, LITERATURE REVIEW AND DISCUSSION

The Problem of the formation today worries not only teacher, but also pupils, their parents, state, one word, all society. The Question is concluded in that to, alongside with ensuring the profound knowledge to develop beside pupils abilities of the thinking and activity practical. The importance in modern condition gains the renovation and revising theorist practical bases of the education and education. Before pedagogical science and system of the formation are put (deliver) tasks to modernizations of the contents and methods of the education, development principle, making the scholastic programs and methodical literature, aiming teacher at shaping beside pupils skill of the assimilation and generalizations of the knowledge, cultures of the contact, education moral quality.

The Modern teacher, especially teacher of the literature, must be poetical adjusted by personality. His (its) task to act upon knowledge-based and emotional sphere pupils. With standpoint of art criticism and literary criticism due to artistic creative activity beside pupils are formed skills of the emotional voluptuous perception of the world, which particularity is concluded in creation bright, demonstrative picture of the world in presentation pupils. Elements find reflection in it fine, moral rates, spiritual feeling. All these feeling and moral criteria each pupil necessary to understand and take for itself. One of the tasks of the course of the methods of the teaching the literature in highest the educational institutions to reflect in contents of the course to particularities of the general culture of Uzbek society. Each representative modern society must adopt his (its) spiritual value. In too time follows to note that today all else exist the certain literary stereo types, contradictions in artistic and pedagogical creative activity. Besides, new type attitude forms in modern pedagogical process between teacher and pupils, when pupils all more orientate on creative quest and by itself decisions of the scholastic tasks. Such approach education requires shaping besides pupils critical thinking, since on lesson of the literature they face with inconsistent nature (the literary hero).

At years of independence of the change concerned in the first place artistic literature. In society was formed new thinking, appeared new value, in literature «came" new hero. Has accordingly occurred the renovation of many scientific disciplines, including methods of the literature. In pedagogical activity of the teachers central place has occupied shaping besides pupils critical thinking, skill by itself to value the literary heroes. Consequently, teacher of the literature must leave for "literary framework" that is to say not only direct pupils on assimilations of the artistic particularities of the product his (its) analysis, and develop skills of the critical estimation of the literary heroes beside them. The Last is connected with need to arm the pupils knowledge about aesthetic, ideological to moral position of the heroes of the literary product and requires the mastering pupils corresponding to approach of the figurative system. In this instance follows to speak of literary and

linguistically analysis artistic product. To organize scholastic activity in specified direction, necessary to create the condition for creative interaction of the teacher and pupils. Necessary to take into account and that fact that modern schoolchildren "remote" from artistic literature and do not strive to deep penetration in essence of the under study product. It Is Required big skill and efforts of the teacher to arouse beside pupils interest to independent reading and form the skills of the perception of the artistic text. For this it is necessary that functioning on artistic product was realized constantly and determined systems. The Analysis of the product must carry on этапной and in too time nature. This and analysis eventful sides, and consideration unity space and time and study of the estimation of the product. For the last ten-year-old (at years of independence) much new products appeared in Uzbek literature that has conditioned arising the new problems in methods of the teaching to literature. We shall Name main of them.

1. The Problem of the study and perceptions of the artistic foresight as art of the word and shaping the spiritual world increasing the frequency of. Much it is important here with to avoid the indifferent attitude pupils to product. On this reasonable use receiving the familiarization with product, which revealed his (its) importance directly for pupil, spurred pupils give the estimation read by product to define their own life purposes and positions on base of the studied product. All these reader's skills interconnected and occupy the important place in process of the independent reading.

2. The Problem of the enrichment pupils scientific knowledge on base interrelation the methods teaching the literature and literary. The Problem of the study artistic product on lesson of the literature and his (its) prospects are today considered in context of the creative thinking on new.

3. The Problem of the provision to independent activity pupils in step of perceptions and analysis of the artistic product, critical estimation of the heroes.

4. The Problem of the development skill critical estimation of the literary heroes' pupils, with the emphasis development exploratory skill. For this teacher

necessary well to know the contents of the school course of the literature, concept to education subject, know how to choose and use efficient innovative technologies.

5. The Problem of the education pupil's acceptance and method of the reading, studies, analysis of the artistic text arms their skill of the critical estimation. The Teacher in turn must know how to design the process of the study of the new material.

6. The Problem of the shaping attitude relations of mutually between teacher and pupils, developments of creative artistic skill besidepupils.

7. The Problem of modelling of the new structure lesson, organizations occupation innovative type, on which teacher addresses to aesthetic, philosophical, history, literary source and uses the nonconventional forms of the education.

The Artistic perception of the material world is one of the facilities of the cognition and comprehensions to cultural life of Uzbek society: Artistic perception to reality concentrates in itself different types of activity, for instance such as scolded transformed, cognition, orientation on value, communication and others.

Relying on modern approaches, possible confirm that between writer and reader not cutting galley proof, since art, including fiction, being product artistic creative activity, is one of the forms of the artistic contact. In process of the reading the literary product pupils enter in contact with author as subjects to communications and through product adopt the system an attitude to objective reality. Consequently, fiction, acting upon consciousnesses of the personalities, executes the public humanistic function. She personifies in itself artistic aesthetic memory of Uzbek folk spiritual and moral value and hereunder serves the all round development to personalities, facility of the shaping critical thinking pupi

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